

Exploring the Moderating Effect of Well-Being on Job Crafting and Retention Outcomes of Healthcare Workers in the Nigerian Healthcare System

¹Nancy I. Tongo

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-0807-2044>

¹Anthonia A. Adeniji

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6936-0563>

¹Odunayo P. Salau

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9514-9427>

^{1,2}Oluwakemi O. Onayemi

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1831-3542>

oluwakemi.onayemi@covenantuniversity.edu.ng (Corresponding author)

¹Oluwatoyin Adesanya

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9253-5795>

¹Business, Entrepreneurship and Innovation Cluster, Covenant University, Ota, Ogun State

²Business Innovation Accelerator, Lagos Business School, Lekki, Lagos

Abstract

Background: Globally, the business environment has become competitive due to innovation and technology, so organisations have resorted to strategic means to remain relevant and retain their workforce. The dynamic business changes heightened by the COVID-19 pandemic have made it clear that sticking to the traditional method of business operation may result in poor retention outcomes.

Objective: This study examined the moderating effect of employees' well-being on the relationship between job crafting and retention outcomes of healthcare workers in public hospitals in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Methodology: The study employed the quantitative research design using primary data. The population of the study comprised all doctors and nurses in the secondary category of public hospitals in Lagos State, with a sample size of 725 determined using Morgan Sample Size

Determination Table. Structural Equation Modelling, specifically, Partial Least Squares Method, was utilised in evaluating the collected data.

Results: Findings reveal that employees' well-being has a small and inverse moderating influence on the relationship between job crafting and retention outcomes, despite directly influencing retention outcomes. The findings contributed to understanding the complex dynamics between job crafting, employees' well-being, and retention outcomes in the Nigerian healthcare system.

Conclusion: Motivating elements must be present for employees' well-being to control the connection between job crafting and retention outcomes successfully.

Recommendations: Regular well-being assessments should be conducted to monitor employees' happiness; interventions should be individualised to meet needs while building a friendly and stimulating work environment that encourages retention by proactively addressing well-being concerns in the organisation.

Unique Contribution: The study found a modest and inverse moderating impact, which raises concerns that depending exclusively on employee well-being as a moderating variable between job crafting and retention outcomes may not be an efficient way to achieve positive retention outcomes.

Key words: General hospitals, healthcare workers, job crafting, retention outcomes, well-being

Introduction

Job crafting has been a recurring construct among scholars and researchers. It is an independently motivated work design process that is proactive and self-initiated by employees to alter the qualities of a job to suit their needs, as well as their skills and goals. This became prominent due to the dynamic changes in businesses as well as the environmental and social changes in the nature of work imposed on firms and organisations due to the pandemic, which saw most businesses going wall-less, a total deviation from the norm, especially in African countries. The concept of job crafting in the healthcare system has been investigated by some scholars (Laker et al., 2020), though using different variables, different geographical locations and not being specific to the levels of the healthcare system.

The healthcare system is a service-oriented sector that requires employees' full attention to function maximally. Due to the overwhelming nature of work in the sector, heightened by the pandemic, poor working conditions and lack of basic infrastructure in most African countries, specifically Nigeria, it has become imperative for work to be redefined, which could greatly impact both the employees and the organisation as a whole. Differently now, contemporary workplaces are increasingly driven by performance metrics due to advancements in technological innovations; a system that now emphasises greater and higher performance of employees, higher personal abilities, high creativity, extremely skilled, resilient, innovative and proactive in service delivery. Therefore, a modern operation characterised by open and collaborative methods is expected for positive retention outcomes.

The well-being of employees in every organisation greatly determines the level of employees' engagement. Past studies have investigated employees' well-being as a prerequisite for overall organisational well-being (Pradhan & Hati, 2019). Usually, the healthcare system functions under intense pressure with no time schedule. This worsened during the COVID-19 pandemic, which resulted in most workers working around the clock. Healthcare workers are expected always to

provide prompt and timely responses to patients because the job demands that patients and customers be promptly attended to, following the normal acceptable standard.

Job crafting, developed by Amy Wrzesniewski and Jane Dutton (2001), was dimensionalised into cognitive, task and relational crafting, and it functions under the concept of job demands and job resources regarded as suitable to meet the high demands and expectations in the health sector (Laker et al., 2020). Based on this background, this study examined the moderating influence of employees' well-being on the relationship between job crafting and retention outcomes of healthcare workers in public hospitals in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Objective

To assess the moderating effect of employees' well-being on the relationship between job crafting and retention outcomes of healthcare workers in public hospitals.

Hypothesis

H₁: Employees' well-being significantly moderates the relationship between job crafting and retention outcomes of healthcare workers in public hospitals.

Literature Review

Overview of Job Crafting

The concept of job crafting, developed in 2001, has continuously received attention from scholars and researchers due to the continuous changes in the business world and the greater awareness of the need to ensure the well-being of employees. Job crafting includes cognitive crafting which is the mental or psychological modification of the job performed by an individual to suit his mental perception (Geldenhuis et al, 2020); task crafting which is the physical alterations of one's job according to one's skills and talent (Hornung, 2019); and relational crafting which is the expansion of one's sphere of contact in the workplace, given him the opportunity to work with employees of like minds (Letona-Ibanez et al, 2019).

The Concept of Well-being

Well-being, on the other hand, has been depicted as a means of providing employees with the opportunity to develop their innate abilities, having the potential to be productive and creative, develop healthy relationships, as well as contribute meaningfully to society (Foresight Mental Capital and Well-being Project; WHO, 2020). Davis (2019) described it as a perception of soundness and strength emanating from one's thoughts, desires, feelings, experiences, actions and emotions. The World Health Organisation (WHO, 2020) attributed healthy living and positive mental state to well-being. This means all-round functionality of an individual emotionally, mentally, physically, economically, socially and psychologically.

The clamour for employees' well-being cannot be overemphasised among healthcare workers, who need to be psychologically, emotionally, physically, and mentally balanced to attend to patients effectively. The sensitive duties of doctors and nurses require a good frame of mind and total well-being of the healthcare worker (Sagherian et al., 2020).

Retention Outcomes

The retention of an organisation's workforce has been considered one of the most widely researched areas in the field of human resources. It is the deliberate process of an organisation to motivate and encourage its human resources to stay in the organisation, for its productivity and growth. The success of any organisation is dependent on how well the employees are empowered and supported with favourable conditions to unleash their full potential (Onifade et al, 2022). It is therefore imperative for the well-being of employees to be prioritised.

Since the COVID-19 pandemic, organisations have seen the need to strategise to ensure the well-being of their employees. Organisations that actively pursue a transition from traditional business operations are more likely to succeed in today's increasingly competitive and dynamic business environment. For a business, hiring skilled employees is critical, but keeping them in their positions is more crucial, especially for the well-being of any nation.

Past research has ascribed many factors to negative retention outcomes (Salau et al., 2020), including a non-conducive working environment, very poor remuneration, restricted and poorly structured jobs, lack of welfare packages, overwhelming work schedule, etc. Therefore, globalisation and evolution in business operations, even in the healthcare system, with employee skill competencies, have necessitated the call for employees to be fully involved in crafting their jobs for positive retention outcomes.

Overview of the Nigerian Healthcare System

The healthcare system's core function is providing healthcare services to people, financing, serving and developing resources. It also contributes to eradicating poverty, improving the growth and well-being of citizens, thereby resulting in a healthy environment in the country. This was spelt out in Goal 3 (three) of the SDG, recommended by WHO, and approved by the United Nations (UN) on September 25th, 2015. Therefore, promoting healthy life and well-being of citizens is one of the top priorities of the SDGs, with emphasis on access to quality healthcare services for everyone without any financial difficulty (Sustainable Development Goal 2020).

Using statistical evidence of various countries' contributions to the SDGs ranked by their overall score in the ranking index, the UK has a total score of 80.55%; the US scored 74.55%, while Finland topped the list with a total contribution of 86.51%. The ranking index showed Nigeria with a total of 54.23%, while Malawi, Sierra Leone and Guinea scored 53.25%, 52.29% and 51.27% respectively (Sustainable Development Goal Report, 2020). This shows that the 17 goals of the SDG and specifically goal 3 (three) are yet to be fully implemented by some African countries, especially Nigeria (Domagala et al., 2022).

Theoretical Justification

Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model

The job demands-resources model was developed by researchers Arnold Bakker and Evangelia Demerouti in 2006 as an alternative to all other models on the well-being of employees. The JD-R model caters to all the possible needs of an organisation. According to the model, working conditions are in two forms: job demands and resources. Job demands are the category of work that makes the employee exert energy, e.g., difficult tasks, work overload and conflict in the

workplace. In contrast, work overload and complexity are jobs that seem challenging to the employees, making them bring out their best in the organisation. However, job resources, which are also called positives, enable employees to handle their job demands effectively to achieve the expected goals in the organisation.

Job crafting functions under the concept of job demands and resources, which is suitable for meeting the high demands and expectations in the healthcare system (Laker *et al.*, 2020). The tight and heavy work schedules without any form of leisure which describes the Nigerian healthcare system is regarded as the job demands and this can only be put in check by the availability of adequate job resources which could be people, medical facilities, working equipment, adequate and conducive work environment as well as better technological system. The absence of job resources affects performance, leading to job burnout and poor retention outcomes. Therefore, there may be a need for the healthcare worker to use greater resources at the individual level to meet the overwhelming nature of work and high job demands.

Methodology

This study adopted an explanatory research design because it assisted the researcher in explicitly explaining the variables under study in a clear and simplistic manner. The study area included all general hospitals, the secondary category of hospitals in Lagos State, Nigeria. The population for the study consisted of all the doctors and nurses in the general hospitals in Lagos State, which was obtained from the Human Resource Department of the hospitals. The population was 4,036 and 7,048 for doctors and nurses, respectively, totalling 11,084. These healthcare workers were selected because they were more affected by the work stress in the healthcare system, leading to their mass resignation.

The sample size was determined using Morgan's Sample Size Determination Table, and at a 95% confidence level, the sample size became 357 and 370 for doctors and nurses, respectively. The study employed a multi-stage sampling technique, and the primary data collection method was utilised. The primary data collection using the quantitative method was done using a questionnaire.

The questionnaire was structured into sections A and B. Section A covered the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Section B was based on the required questions about the various objectives of the study, as well as other relevant information related to the construct of the study (job crafting, employees' well-being and retention outcomes), respectively. A five (5) point Likert scale (which ranged from 1: Strongly Disagree and 5: Strongly Agree) was adopted to measure the various responses from respondents.

The data obtained was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, which involved frequency distribution tables and simple percentages, with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. Statistical tools for analysing the study's stated hypothesis include structural equation modelling and the partial least squares method.

Results and Analysis

The unit of analysis for this study was all the medical doctors and nurses in the General Hospital in Lagos State, Nigeria. Using the Morgan sample size distribution table, the sample size was 725.

Descriptive Statistics

Tables 1, 2 and 3 depict the statistical descriptions of economic, psychological and social well-being, respectively.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Economic Well-being

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Un-decided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Economic Well-being						
My living standard has improved in the past six months	185 (29%)	200 (31%)	76 (12%)	94 (15%)	90 (14%)	645 (100%)
My level of income impacts my health positively	173 (27%)	74 (12%)	173 (27%)	111 (17%)	114 (18%)	645 (100%)
My financial stability makes me feel optimistic about the future	191 (30%)	152 (23.6%)	100 (16%)	94 (15%)	108 (17%)	645 (100%)

The findings, as shown in Table 1, suggest that a significant number (60%) feel that their living standard has improved in the past six months, which indicates a positive change in their overall quality of life. However, a notable segment (27%) expressed a neutral stance or disagreement, suggesting that not all healthcare workers have experienced the same level of improvement.

In terms of income and its impact on health, a significant proportion of healthcare workers (39%) believe that their income level positively affects their health. This highlights the perceived link between financial stability and well-being. However, there is also a notable segment (29%) who expressed a neutral stance or disagreement, indicating that not all health workers perceive such an impact. Regarding financial stability and optimism about the future, many healthcare workers (53%) state that their financial stability makes them feel optimistic. This indicates a sense of security and confidence in their future prospects. However, there is also a segment (32%) that expressed a neutral stance or disagreement.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Psychological Well-being

Psychological Well-being	Strongly Agree	Agree	Un-decided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
I feel a sense of purpose in life due to my job tasks	173 (27%)	226 (35%)	64 (10%)	84 (13%)	98 (15%)	645 (100%)
I am satisfied with my professional development and growth.	189 (29%)	218 (34%)	62 (10%)	83 (13%)	93 (14%)	645 (100%)
I am satisfied with how autonomous my job tasks are.	167 (26%)	234 (36%)	65 (10%)	81 (13%)	98 (15%)	645 (100%)

Table 2 findings regarding the sense of purpose in life due to job tasks indicate that many healthcare workers (62%) feel a sense of purpose derived from their work. This reflects their meaningfulness in their job tasks, contributing to a sense of fulfilment and motivation. However, a segment (25%) expresses a neutral stance or disagreement.

Regarding professional development and growth, a considerable proportion of healthcare workers (63%) report satisfaction with their professional development. This indicates that their skills and knowledge are advancing, contributing to their overall job satisfaction. However, a segment (24%) also expressed a neutral stance or disagreement.

Regarding job autonomy, a significant number of healthcare workers (62%) express satisfaction with their level of autonomy in their job tasks. This suggests that they feel empowered and have a degree of control in their work, which can enhance job satisfaction and motivation. However, a segment (23%) also expresses a neutral stance or disagreement on the level of autonomy.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for Social Well-being

Social Well-being	Strongly Agree	Agree	Un-decided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
The positive relationships I cultivate at work give me confidence.	218 (34%)	193 (30%)	69 (11%)	90 (14%)	75 (12%)	645 (100%)
I sustain meaningful relationships with my patients	192 (30%)	212 (33%)	75 (12%)	88 (14%)	78 (12%)	645 (100%)
I show respect for diversity regardless of our differences	195 (30%)	211 (33%)	78 (12%)	80 (12%)	81 (13%)	645 (100%)

According to the findings as presented in Table 3, many healthcare workers (64%) express that their positive relationships at work give them confidence. Regarding relationships with patients, a considerable portion of healthcare workers (63%) report sustaining meaningful relationships with their patients. On respecting diversity, many healthcare workers (63%) show respect for diversity regardless of differences. |

Test of Hypothesis

H₀: Employees’ well-being does not have a significant influence on job crafting and retention outcomes of healthcare workers (doctors and nurses)

The hypothesis consists of one independent variable, job crafting, one moderating variable (employees’ well-being) and one dependent variable, the retention outcomes. All the variables in the study were assessed using a structured questionnaire employing a five-point Likert scale.

PLS-SEM is commonly used to predict the relationship between variables (Hair et al., 2022). The structural equation modelling of the hypothesis, presented in Figure 1, illustrates the standardised estimates that indicate the moderating impact of employees’ well-being on job crafting and retention outcomes of healthcare workers in public hospitals, Lagos State, Nigeria. It is important to note that all the items related to employees’ well-being, job crafting and retention outcomes of healthcare workers, as shown in Table 4, exhibited factor loadings above the minimum threshold of 0.70 suggested by Kilic et al. (2020).

Table 4: Factor Loading for Job crafting and Retention outcomes of healthcare workers

Indicators	Factor Loading	Error Variance	Composite Reliability	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Indicators
Job Crafting			0.831	0.628	0.803	15
Relational Crafting	0.726	0.271				
Task crafting	0.888	0.104				
Cognitive Crafting	0.840	0.158				
Employees' wellbeing			0.831	0.628	0.803	9
Social well-being	0.733	0.267				
Economic well-being	0.836	0.164				
Psychological well-being	0.842	0.158				
Retention Outcomes	0.897	0.103	0.831	0.628	0.803	15

According to Kilic et al. (2020), factor loadings should surpass the threshold of 0.70, composite reliability should be at least 0.80 (ideally higher), and the average variance extracted (AVE) should exceed the minimum value of 0.50. Additionally, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient should be equal to or higher than 0.70 for the instruments to be considered reliable. Table 4 displays that all dimensions related to job crafting, employees' well-being and the retention outcomes have values exceeding 0.80 and 0.70, respectively. This indicates that the constructs ranged from 0.726 to 0.888, implying good reliability. With the degree of fit meeting the necessary criteria, the instrument can be considered both valid and reliable.

Evaluation of the Inner Structural Model

The inner structural model was employed to determine the significance of the path coefficients. In PLS-SEM, the use of bootstrapping becomes crucial in assessing the level of significance. In this study, 5000 subsamples were utilised for the default bootstrapping. The inner structural model demonstrates the moderating impact of employees' well-being on job crafting and retention outcomes of healthcare workers in public hospitals, Lagos State, Nigeria, are presented in Table 4 and visualised in Figures 1, 2 and 3.

Figure 1 Predictive relevance (Path co-efficient) of Job crafting and Retention outcomes of healthcare workers

(b) Path Coefficients (β) and T-statistics estimation

The path coefficients and the standardised coefficient were obtained using Partial Least Square. The value was used to test the hypothesis's significance. The bigger the value, the more significant the influence on the retention outcomes. However, in Figures 2 and 3, bootstrapping depicted for job crafting dimensions, employees' wellbeing dimensions and retention outcomes in the Public Hospitals in Lagos State, Nigeria was presented.

Figure 2: Path Co-efficient and T-values for Job crafting and Retention outcomes of healthcare workers

Figure 3: Path Co-efficient and P-values for Job crafting and Retention outcomes of healthcare workers

Discussion

According to the research's results, job crafting, including relational, task, and cognitive crafting and retention outcomes for healthcare workers working in public hospitals play a moderating role in this connection. Particularly, economic well-being, followed by social and psychological well-being, appeared as the best predictor. It is interesting to note that the study found that employees' well-being had a small and inverse moderating influence. This indicates that the retention rates of healthcare workers tend to decline when the well-being of staff is used as a moderating variable in public hospitals. Therefore, even while employees' well-being has a considerable impact on

healthcare workers' retention rate, it is unable to successfully control this connection in public hospitals unless specific motivating elements are in place.

Studies have investigated the effects of employees' well-being on positive outcomes. Sesario et al, (2024), investigated the influence of compensation, work environment, performance and discipline on the performance of Agribusiness employees, and findings revealed that these factors positively impacted employees' performance. Also, Adekoya et al (2019) investigated the significance of employee engagement and individual well-being on organisational performance in Nigeria using data collected from 48 respondents through the administration of semi-structured questionnaires and interviews from one of the top plastic manufacturing companies in Nigeria. They discovered that employees' efficiency and effectiveness were impacted by individual well-being through elements like work-life balance and job satisfaction, which would ultimately enhance organisational productivity. This bolsters the notion that an employee's desire to stay in their job is significantly influenced by how well they are doing. Yoon et al. (2019) studied how employees' job crafting and job satisfaction in multinational corporations affect their well-being using quantitative analysis. Despite not focusing explicitly on health professionals employed in public hospitals, findings revealed that job crafting behaviours had a favourable impact on well-being and, in turn, had a knock-on effect on retention. This implies that job crafting may enhance workers' well-being, influencing their choice to stay with the organisation.

The discovery that employees' well-being has a modest and negative moderating influence on the association between job crafting and retention outcomes in Public Hospitals is interesting. Nevertheless, this shows that improving retention outcomes might not only require the consideration of employees' well-being as a moderating component. The implementation of additional driving elements, such as chances for growth and development, competitive pay, and building a supportive work environment, may be necessary to favorably impact retention. A further important aspect affecting retention is providing competitive remuneration (Gordon et al, 2018). Public hospitals must make sure that their pay scales reflect industry norms and workers are fairly compensated for their abilities and efforts. Competitive pay not only draws top talent but also motivates workers to stay in their positions.

Fostering a supportive work environment is essential for improving retention outcomes, in addition to providing possibilities for advancement and competitive pay (Salau et al., 2020). Employees are more likely to create a sense of loyalty and dedication when they feel appreciated, respected, and supported by their company and coworkers. Effective communication, praising success, and encouraging work-life balance are all ways to foster a healthy work environment. Public Hospitals can have beneficial and positive retention outcomes by putting these motivational aspects into practice while considering the well-being of their workers. It is necessary to note that these variables may change depending on the organisational setting and the requirements and preferences of healthcare workers. Therefore, a comprehensive strategy that considers several aspects of retention is required.

The findings of the study suggest that employees' well-being moderates the association between job crafting and retention outcomes of healthcare workers in public hospitals. However, the moderating impact is minimal and inverse, indicating that using well-being as the only moderating

variable may not be an efficient way to improve retention. Implementing other motivational elements, such as growth possibilities and a supportive work environment, besides employees' well-being, is critical to enhancing retention outcomes. Further investigation is required to examine and pinpoint the precise variables that, in the setting of public hospitals, might successfully modulate the link between job crafting and retention outcomes.

Theoretical Implication

According to the JD-R Model, which was created by Bakker and Demerouti (2007), the impacts of work demands and job resources on employees' well-being and results are different. The study's findings support the JD-R Model by demonstrating how job crafting activities, which entail changing task assignments, social contacts, and cognitive components of the job, substantially influence healthcare workers' job satisfaction in public hospitals. Employees actively develop resources and lower expectations by engaging in job crafting, which raises satisfaction levels.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study's conclusions highlight the fact that the well-being of the staff significantly influences retention outcomes for healthcare workers. The discovery of a modest and inverse moderating impact, however, raises concerns that depending exclusively on employee well-being as a moderating variable may not be an efficient way to achieve positive retention outcomes. To enhance retention outcomes, it is essential to provide extra motivational elements, such as growth possibilities, competitive pay, and building a supportive work environment.

The study recommends that public hospitals conduct routine well-being assessments to monitor the happiness of their staff members. This will give insights into areas of concern and assist in the identification of appropriate solutions to improve employees' well-being.

Interventions should be individualised to meet needs, as healthcare workers' requirements and interests vary. Offering flexibility and customisation in terms of working conditions, perks, and career possibilities may show that a business respects and supports each employee's particular situation. The healthcare sector should give this top priority while assuring the provision of high-quality healthcare services.

Contribution to Knowledge

The link between job crafting, employees' well-being, and retention outcomes of healthcare workers in public hospitals was discussed empirically in this study's findings, which add to the body of knowledge in this area. To comprehend and enhance employee retention outcomes in the healthcare system, the findings provided insightful information and practical consequences for researchers and practitioners. The findings also provided a roadmap for managers of Public Hospitals in developing countries. The suggestions can guide managers in developing a welcoming work environment and implementing tactics that enhance employees' satisfaction, well-being, and positive retention outcomes.

References

- Adekoya, O. D., Jimoh, I., Okorie, G., & Olajide, M. (2019). Significance of employee engagement and employee well-being on organisational performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies.*, 2(5), 34-47.
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2017). Job demands-resources theory: Taking stock and looking forward. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 22, 273-285.
- Davies, T. (2019). *What is well-being? Definition, types and well-being skills*. Retrieved April 14, 2022, from <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/click-here-happiness/201901/what-is-well-being-definition-types-and-well-being-skills>
- Domagala, A., Kautsch, M., Kulbat, A., & Parzonka, K. (2022). Exploration of estimated emmigration trends of Polish Health Professionals. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(2), 940-945.
- Geldenhuis, M., Bakker, A., & Demerouti, E. (2020). How task, relational and cognitive crafting, relate to job performance: A weekly diary study on the role of meaningfulness. *European Journal of Work and Organisational Psychology*, 30(1), 83-94.
- Gordon, H. J., Demerouti, E., Le Blanc, P. E., Bakker, A. B., Bipp, T., & MarcVehergen, A. M. (2018). Individual job redesign: Job crafting intervention in the healthcare. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 104, 98-144.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2022). *A Primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling PLS-SEM* (3 ed.). Sage.
- Hornung, S. (2019). Crafting task and cognitive job boundaries to enhance self determination, impact, meaning and competence at work. *Journal of Behavioural Sciences*, 9(12), 136-145.
- Kilic, A. F., Uysal, I., & Atar, B. (2020). Comparison of confirmatory factor analysis estimation methods on binary data. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 7(3), 451-487.
- Laker, B., Patel, C., Budhwar, P., & Malik, A. (2020). *How job crafting can make work more satisfying*. Retrieved May 12, 2022, from MITSloan Management Review: <https://www.centaur.reading.ac.uk/92117/>.
- Leona-Ibanez, O., Garrasco, M., Martinez-Rodriguez, S., Ammilano, A., & Ortiz-Marques, N. (2019). Cognitive, relational and task crafting: Spanish adaptation and analysis of psychometric properties of the job crafting questionnaire. *Plus ONE*, 14(10), 1-15.
- Onifade, T. A., Tongo, N. I., & Adetayo, H. O. (2022). The effect of knowledge sharing and protection on organisational performance in selected money deposit banks in Lagos Nigeria. *Journal of Academic Research in Economics*, 4(1), 153-163.

- Pradhan, R. K., & Hati, L. (2019). The measurement of employee well-being: Development and validation of a scale. *Global Business Review*, 23(1), 1-23.
- Sagherian, K., Steege, L. M., Cobb, S. J., & Cho, H. (2020). *Insomnia, fatigue and psychosocio well-being during Covid-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional survey of hospital nursing staff in the United States*. Retrieved May 12, 2022, from National Library of Medicine: <https://www.pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- Salau, O., Worlu, R., Osinbajo, A., Adeniji, A., ..., & Ogueyungbo, O. (2020). The impact of workplace environments on retention outcomes of public Universities in Southern Nigeria. *SAGE Open*, 10(2), 21-32.
- Sesario, R., Fatimah, M. L., Ali, Z. A., Musram, M., & La-Ode, M. (2024). Analysis of the influence of compensation, work discipline and work environment on performance of National Agribusiness Company Employees. *JEMSI*, 10(1), 78-83.
- Sustainable Developmental Goal (SDG). (2020). *The sustainable developmental report and Covid-19*. Retrieved June 17, 2022, from <https://www.sdgindex.org>
- World Health Organisation (WHO). (2020). *World Health Organisation Statistics*. Retrieved June 6, 2022, from WHO International Web site: <https://who.int/doc/default-source/gho-documents/world-health-statistics-reports/6-june-20108-world-health-statistics-2020pdf>.
- Wrzesniewski, A., & Dutton, J. E. (2001). Crafting a job: Revisioning employees as active crafters of their work. *Academy of Management Review*, 26(2), 179-201.
- Yoon, K., Kim, B., & EOM, J. (2019). The effect of job crafting career success of multinational corporation's employees. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 6(4), 213-225.